

Future-proofing science education using real-life issues in open-schooling

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Abstract. This paper outlines open schooling as an innovative approach to education that adequately prepares students for the future, both in terms of knowledge and skills acquisition. It presents the CONNECT project as an inclusive, engaging and future-oriented approach to open-schooling. The project resources include 'science-actions', based on real-life socio-scientific issues and a new pedagogical framework (CARE-KNOW-DO) that increases active engagement and supports problem-solving in the classroom. The findings of the project, used by teachers across Europe and Brazil, show that its aims of improving knowledge and skills, increasing effective engagement, raising aspirations, and promoting science in student's lives were met, and highlights the transformative potential of open schooling.

1. Introduction

Is a traditional transmissive curriculum adequately preparing our children? In a constantly evolving world where climate and sustainability issues are at the forefront as well as the advancing scope of technology, what changes need to be made by us, as educators, to prepare them to be responsible citizens in an uncertain future?

Our argument is that a traditional curriculum is not able to meet their needs; it doesn't consider what issues students care about and what knowledge and skills they need to develop. Many students are also under-served (mainly those from a low socioeconomic background) lacking cultural familiarity with scientific thinking and adequate role models, with limited opportunities to engage with natural, formal and human sciences beyond formal education for shape better lives and desirable future.

These factors combined often lead to a significant number of students feeling a disconnect between what they learn in the classroom and what they experience in their lives. This can manifest itself as a disinterest in science, a feeling that it is 'not for me' and ultimately an unwillingness to pursue science into higher education, as a career and citizenship.

In CONNECT we introduced teachers from across Europe and Brazil, to an approach – open schooling, which aims to address these concerns. We combined this with a new pedagogical framework for open schooling teaching – CARE-KNOW-DO. Both can be used in primary and secondary classrooms to help increase affective engagement and inspire students to explore the world through the lens of science and scientific thinking.

Our aims were to:

- Introduce teachers to the benefits of open-schooling.
- Implement a pedagogical framework for science teaching (CARE-KNOW-DO) that increases active engagement and supports real-life problem-solving.
- Improve the knowledge, skills and aspirations of students, especially those that are under-served.

2. Principles: CARE-KNOW-DO framework

Open-schooling is about solving real-life challenges to enhance wellbeing and sustainability by bringing together students with teachers, scientists, family members and policymakers. In CONNECT we provided guidance to teachers taking their first steps into open-schooling by removing barriers and providing engaging, participatory approaches called ‘science-actions’.

CARE-KNOW-DO (Fig. 1) aims to make science education more meaningful, engaging, and relevant for students by supporting problem-solving based on real-world issues and fostering a sense of ownership and agency in their learning process supported by professionals and family members.

As the name suggests, there are three stages:

Figure 1: CARE-KNOW-DO for open schooling in the CONNECT project

The CARE stage introduces students to the issue and sets a challenge. In CONNECT, we choose issues related to the environment and health, focusing on current and relevant topics that align with students' concerns and interests. Scientists, who are either invited into the classroom or featured in recorded interviews, discuss their research, and students are given a simple yet engaging activity to take home and share with their families to stimulate discussions about the issue.

The KNOW stage primarily involves formal teaching of the curriculum, emphasizing the acquisition of knowledge and skills necessary to understand the issue and participate in discussions regarding potential solutions. As students apply their newfound knowledge to the issue, they transition from surface-level understanding of scientific concepts to deep and transferable knowledge.

The DO stage represents the final phase, where students utilize their recently acquired knowledge and skills to collaboratively address the issue. They present their actions either verbally or in writing. These ideas may be discussed at home or at school, including conversations with scientists. Teachers utilize these presentations as means to assess comprehension and engagement.

We employed the CARE-KNOW-DO framework [1] to develop a collection of high-quality open schooling resources. These materials are user-friendly and inclusive, varying in length, making them suitable for a diverse range of classrooms, as illustrated in Figure 2. Collectively, they address a wide array of issues and curriculum areas, providing opportunities for learning and applying inquiry, mathematical, and communication skills.

Teachers have embraced these learning resources in their planning, whether for single lessons, extended projects, or comprehensive units of study. This adoption aims to enhance student participation in science

activities, enabling them to transition from passive learners to active participants who take on roles as investigators, critical thinkers, co-creators of knowledge, and problem solvers.

Participatory Science with Open Schooling

Rewilding	Microplastics	Energy savers	Poo transplants	Carbon neutral	Inquiry Map	System dialogue	Projects
Food webs Competition	Particle model Mixtures	Energy transfer Energy efficiency	Digestion	Climate change	Deliberative Mapping	Participatory Action Research	Community-based learning
Maps for solutions	CO2 x infections	Handwashing	Healthy Minds	White Plastics	Jury	Consensus	Cocreation
Sustainability	Health issues	Health Protection	Mental Health	Pollution	Citizen Jury	Consensus Conference	World Café, Participatory design

Structured Curriculum Materials
Inspired by the ENGAGE, CRISS and XploreHealth projects

Open Scenario Tools
Inspired by the Engage2020 project

Figure 2: Some examples of CONNECT Multi-Language Open schooling resources

To create the open schooling resources, we used a ‘backwards design’ approach, where we started with the goals for each stage, and using research-based and participatory design pedagogies, created the activities that would achieve them. These resources grouped into two categories (structured curriculum materials and open scenario tools), freely available to download from the CONNECT platform <https://connect-eu.exus.co.uk/category/english/>, were extensively used by students integrated to their formal curriculum supported by teachers, non-formal experts from organisations and informal educators from families and local communities. These resulted in a variety of science actions led by students in five countries. Some examples are available on CONNECT website (<https://www.connect-science.net/best-practices/>). As part of the open science approach with just-in-time feedback schools coordinators and their communities were able to access the project’s report responded by teachers and by students available on the [GoogleMap](#).

3. Methodology

The research approach of the CONNECT project prioritized the support of open schooling planning, implementation, and assessment, emphasizing refinement and evidence-based impact. Our approach, centred on a mixed methods study, aimed to inform both the scientific research community and research-based practitioners. Qualitative methods such as interviews and observations provided in-depth perspectives, while quantitative methods, supported by the CONNECT-science instrument, participatory science approaches [3] [4], were grounded in science capital and affective engagement [5], facilitating scalability. Access to evidence from mixed-method studies proved essential for educators and policymakers, enabling them to make informed decisions regarding the adoption and sustainability of open schooling within their organizations.

4. Key findings

More than 30,000 students took part in a CONNECT open-schooling project. A total of 16,716 students-participants across Europe and Brazil aged between 7 and 19 completed their science actions and completed the CONNECT research instrument on a voluntary basis. Linking to our aim of promoting open schooling with under-served students, most attended a state school (95%), only 18% had parents

in jobs that use science, 50% didn't do science activities outside of school and 31% didn't have access to the internet at home [5].

4.1 CONNECT platform

A large number of educators from formal and non-formal sectors including teachers, academics, researchers, scientists, teachers' educators, policymakers such as school heads and science coordinators totalise 1751 members, with an increasing number in phase 3 (2023)

Figure 3: CONNECT platform Analytics

4.2 CONNECT Social Media platform

CONNECT website connected with social networks established collaborations with a large number of national organisations GO and NGO, including an increasing number of followers in social media (table 1)

Connect Project EU Overview							
Social Media	Posts	Followers	Reactions	Comments	Shares	Engagement	Reach
Facebook	248	2,583	31,940	152	129	32,221	466,925
Instagram	76	62	7,872	3	11	7,886	652,214
Linkedin	242	145	470	3	38	511	11,644
Twitter	294	1,117	11,578	61	321	11,960	937,625
TOTAL	860	3,907	51,860	219	499	52,578	2,068,408

Table 1: CONNECT website and social media

4.3 CONNECT Best practices.

Figure 5 shows two examples of a science action focused on Rewilding. The real-life issue is the controversy over rewilding projects where extinct animal species are reintroduced to ecosystems for the benefit of wildlife, people, and climate. The Rewilding science-action encouraged students to use their understanding of interdependence and evidence analysis skills to plan a campaign promoting the rewilding of an animal into their country forests.

The activities designed, parts of which are shown as Figure 5 on the left, included examining how the reintroduction of wolves into an elk-populated national park restored the biodiversity balance, using a woodland food web to predict the effects of rewilding on the ecosystem's organisms and analysing data collected by scientists on the effects of the rewilding of beavers into a UK river. Figure 5 on the right shows an inquiry map produced by AI to explore these Brazilian students' questions "Can the reintroduction of a specific animal in the Pantanal increase tree and plant fruit production, benefiting the food web and potentially leading to a higher number of birds and mammals in the ecosystem? Which animals are recommended for this purpose?"

In carrying out these tasks, students applied their knowledge of food webs and competition to gain a deeper understanding of the concepts as well as practicing analysing data using inquiry mapping [5] based on local habitats and issues faced in their countries, learning how to weigh up evidence for conclusions and writing a persuasive argument.

Figure 5 (Left): “Rewilding Wolves to restore UK forests” by British students’ paper campaign (and Right) “Rewilding Peccary(Queixada) to restore Wetlands” by Brazilians’ digital campaign [5]

4.4 CONNECT-science instrument

A summary of the key findings is shown as Figure 6 with a total of 16716 students (October 2023).

Figure 6: Key findings from the CONNECT project

Quantitative findings indicate four key benefits described as follows.

1. Improving knowledge and skills

CARE: After completing a science-action, the majority of students saw the value in science with 80% agreeing that learning science will be useful in their everyday life and 84% reported that knowing science helps people to make decisions.

KNOW: Just over half of students feel confident with their knowledge in science (54%) and in using science to come up with questions and ideas (52%).

DO: Around half of students felt confident doing science projects (53%) but less than a half felt able to talk about science (44%).

This data shows that students see the importance of science but more needs to be done to improve their confidence in their science knowledge and skills.

2. Increasing effective engagement

63% of students said that learning science is fun, with 83% expressing an interest in completing more similar science activities.

This high level of affective engagement is crucial role to foster intrinsic motivation, promote deep learning, and enhance overall learning outcomes.

3. Raising aspirations

43% of students said they would like a job in science, with 39% saying they would like to be seen as a science expert.

This highlights just how successful CONNECT has been in raising aspirations. The Aspires 2 project carried out by UCL in 2020, showed that just 16% of UK students aged 10-18 aspired to work in science [2].

4. Promoting science in students' lives

After completing a science-action, most students reported their family think science is important for the future (62%). 48% of students know someone working with science. As only 18% have parents who work in science, this highlights the positive impact the project had on their interaction with scientists.

Qualitative findings complement and offer detailed insights into the outcomes that have had an impact on students' learning experiences and their connection with science in their daily lives, as described below. The teachers and students who participated showed great enthusiasm for the utilization of open schooling and its advantages. They emphasized multiple educational benefits, including increased parental involvement, enhanced student progress, the presence of scientists, the notion that science can be enjoyable and entertaining, improved group work and independent data retrieval skills among students, heightened awareness of science-related careers, the recognition that scientific knowledge is empowering, enhanced comprehension and self-efficacy in science, the ability to formulate more precise and insightful questions, a greater commitment to environmental care, as well as heightened engagement, curiosity, and active participation.

“**The involvement of parents** was evident in the entire class. I witnessed the **students' progress** in using evidence from various sources to support their claims. The **presence of a scientist** through Zoom added credibility to the project, and the students were actively engaged by it.” Biology Educator (Female), UK. “I learned from scientists that **science can be enjoyable and fun**. Being able to **work in groups** and **find data** ourselves.” Students' 14 years old female UK

“I believe that if we could raise more awareness, more people would **pursue careers in this field**, as it holds significant value for our brains and minds, opening our eyes to the world. **Scientific knowledge is power** when it comes to solving social problems.” Student 17 female Brazil.

“I learned the foundations and principles of how science is vital in our lives and realised the need to improve our **understanding** of it. Through interactions with scientists, I discovered that unfortunately, science is not widely recognized or promoted in our region.” Student 18 male Brazil Northeast

“I learned to **ASK MORE**. With the scientists I learned that science is something interesting and good to study, with the family we learned that it is important to **take care of the Environment**.” Student, male, 11 years old; private school, parents don't work in science Brazil SoutEast.

“Science and technology are part of our lives and using them in a way that adds value is important. Even though at first students **wondered** “Can I do this?” “Will I be able to do it well?” “How can I do it

better? “, the freedom to experiment, the accessibility of the platform, the ease of use and their **engagement** led to positive feedback.” open schooling teacher from Romania.

“It was interesting to see how the students **gradually engaged** during the activities, especially the debates. At first, there was some reluctance to participate in the discussions, perhaps for fear of not having their position respected or valued. When they realised that their contributions were accepted and taken into account, more and more students decided to **present their positions**. The students were very **interested** in the topics under discussion”. Open schooling teacher from Catalunya

5. Conclusions

Our findings from the CONNECT project highlights the transformative potential of open schooling, and also highlights several important questions:

- How can we encourage more schools to adopt aspects of open schooling?
- What strategies can be implemented to effectively incorporate scientific issues that students care about into the curriculum?
- How can we further strengthen links between students, teachers, families and scientists to raise aspirations within science?

These questions will underpin the next phase of our work.

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